

DIGITAL ECONOMY AND ITS ADVANTAGES

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Abstract: This article analyzes the concept of digital economy and its role and advantages in the economy.

Keywords: digital technologies, e-commerce, blockchain, digital economy, cloud computing, artificial intelligence, financial services.

Introduction.

According to the "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy in our country, digitalization of economic sectors and regions, introduction of state information systems and electronic services, as well as public education, public services, judiciary, finance and complex measures are being implemented in the banking system.

At the same time, the lack of an effective rating system for the development of the digital economy and electronic government, as well as an interagency mechanism for its implementation, prevents a deep analysis of the current state of the digital transformation of economic sectors and regions.

Decisions were made by the Cabinet of Ministers in order to introduce an effective system of interdepartmental coordination of evaluation processes for the development of sectoral and regional programs of digital development in the future by introducing a unified rating and evaluation system for assessing the state of digital economy and e-government development in economic sectors, social spheres and regions .

Digital economy is a new form of economy created and developed using digital technologies, internet and information communication technologies (ICT). Information, digital platforms, online services and technological infrastructures occupy a central place in the digital economy. In such an economy, along with traditional industry, trade and services, new, innovative industries will also develop. The main elements of the digital economy:

Electronic commerce (e-commerce): The main form of trade in the digital economy is carried out over the Internet. Electronic commerce, in turn, includes online sales of goods and services, electronic payment systems, and logistics networks.

Mutual trade is also carried out between users from other parties (B2B, B2C, C2C). Popular e-commerce platforms: Amazon, Alibaba, eBay, etc.

Fintech (financial technology): Fintech is a set of technologies aimed at modernizing and digitizing financial services. For example, mobile payments, cryptocurrencies, blockchain technologies, robo-financial advice, etc.

People and businesses can now transfer money, get loans, make investments and perform other financial transactions outside of traditional banking systems.

Blockchain technologies: Blockchain is a decentralized method of securely storing and exchanging data, mostly associated with cryptocurrencies (Bitcoin, Ethereum) and other digital assets.

Blockchain technology enables reliable and transparent transactions on the Internet, and this is causing major reforms, especially in finance, logistics, healthcare and other fields.

Artificial intelligence (AI) and automation: In the digital economy, artificial intelligence and automation technologies are widely used in manufacturing, services and data analysis. These technologies increase work efficiency, simplify operations and improve user experience. For example, manufacturing processes are accelerated with the help of automation, and AI is used to manage customer services (chatbots) and analytics.

Internet of Things (IoT): The Internet of Things (IoT) is a network of "smart" devices that all communicate and share data with each other over the Internet. For example, smart home systems, industrial IoT devices, cars and other products. IoT creates new opportunities in the digital economy, for example, automatic control systems in the automotive industry, remote monitoring in healthcare, as well as increased efficiency in production.

Data and its use (Big Data): Data plays a huge role in the digital economy. With the help of Big Data technologies, big data is analyzed and used for making business decisions. By performing data analysis, companies will be able to understand user behavior, identify new trends, and develop effective marketing strategies.

Cloud Computing: Cloud computing technologies provide the ability to store servers and data over the Internet, which allows businesses to reduce operating costs and provide expanded access to information. In the digital economy, cloud technologies provide opportunities for rapid storage, transfer and analysis of data for businesses and individuals.

Literature review:

Erik Brynjolfsson and Andrew McAfee (USA)

In *The Second Machine Age: Work, Progress, and Prosperity in a Time of Brilliant Technologies* (2014), Erik Brynjolfsson and Andrew McAfee examine

the impact of the digital economy and new technologies. They analyze how the digital economy and artificial intelligence will affect economic growth, the creation of new jobs, as well as the disappearance of certain occupations.

David Autor (USA)

David Autor is an economist and labor market researcher. His works analyze the impact of the digital economy and automation processes on jobs. In particular, he emphasizes the need for digital technologies and automation to train and retrain workers for new skills.

Hal Varian (USA)

Hal Varian is an economist and author of *Information Rules: A Strategic Guide to the Network Economy* (1998). It analyzes the impact of information technologies on the economy, the value of information and the structure of the market for digital products and services.

Advantages of digital economy:

Efficiency and effectiveness: In the digital economy, many processes are automated and optimized for companies and users, which reduces costs and improves work efficiency.

Opportunities to enter international markets: Small businesses will also have the opportunity to enter the global market through digital trading platforms and e-commerce.

Creation of new jobs: The digital economy creates new industries and jobs, for example in IT, artificial intelligence development, digital marketing, etc.

Innovative development: Technologies and innovations develop new forms of economy and create new business models.

Problems and risks of the digital economy:

Security and Privacy: The security of digital systems and the privacy of users must be protected. There are challenges and threats in the field of cyber security.

Digital divide: Not all people in every country or social group have equal access to digital technologies and the Internet. This disparity can lead to economic and social inequality.

Automation and job losses: Advances in artificial intelligence and robotics may lead to the loss of certain occupations, requiring reskilling of workers.

Regulations and Laws:

With the rapid growth of the digital economy, it is necessary to develop laws and regulations to manage new technologies. There is a lack of clear regulation in areas such as cryptocurrencies, blockchain, data protection. Development of the

digital economy means ensuring the growth of the economy in a country or region based on digital technologies, the Internet and innovative approaches. For the development of the digital economy, it is necessary to consider several important directions, because this process includes not only technological innovations, but also the social, economic and political environment. Below are the main ways and strategies for the development of the digital economy:

Digital infrastructure and Internet expansion: The foundation of the digital economy is having a fast and reliable Internet network. For this:

Expanding access to the Internet: It is necessary to increase the access of the population to the Internet by developing mass Internet providers and mobile communication services. In order to reduce interregional disparities, it is necessary to provide information technology with affordable prices and high quality services.

Implementation of 5G and new technologies: Increasing the speed and quality of the Internet by deploying new technologies, including 5G, which will accelerate digital services and commerce.

Wide use of information and communication technologies (ICT): Information technologies play a key role in the development of the digital economy. To this end:

E-tutoring and e-learning: Incorporating digital tools into the education system, increasing learning opportunities using online courses and platforms.

Digital Services and Commerce: Development of digital services (e.g. public services, healthcare, banking) and e-commerce platforms. In e-commerce, for example, it is necessary to create favorable conditions for small and medium-sized businesses to sell goods and services online.

Development of innovative technologies and attraction of investments.

Startups and Creating an Innovation Ecosystem: Creating an innovation ecosystem is important for the development of the digital economy. It is necessary to support new start-ups, establish start-up incubators, technology parks and research centers.

Investment in cryptocurrencies and blockchain technologies: Cryptocurrencies and blockchain technologies create new economic opportunities. For their development, it is necessary to attract investors and regulate the industry.

Development of digital skills: For the successful development of the digital economy, it is necessary to develop the skills of human resources:

Improving digital skills in the education system: Adapting curricula and training to the needs of the digital economy. Expanding educational opportunities in

areas such as programming, artificial intelligence, data analysis (Big Data), cyber literacy.

Vocational education and reskilling: As automation and artificial intelligence advances, older occupations may disappear. Therefore, it is necessary to re-skill and retrain people for new, digital fields.

Development of financial and digital payment systems:

Fintech (financial technology) development: Digitization of financial services and payment systems. For example, the introduction of mobile banking, cryptocurrency operations and digital payment systems, which will create an opportunity to work efficiently in other areas of the economy.

Ensuring economic stability: The digital economy requires financial integration and secure systems. Central banks and other financial organizations should develop regulations for the development of digital currencies and financial services.

Digitization of health and public services:

Telemedicine and digital health services: Services such as remote diagnosis, consultations, online ordering of medicines should be introduced into the health system with the help of digital technologies.

Digital government services: Digitization of government services, such as simplifying assistance provided to citizens through online document retrieval, tax payments and other government services. This makes communication with the state easier and reduces corruption.

Ensuring cyber security:

Secure infrastructure: Important steps must be taken to ensure the security of information technology, which is a key part of the digital economy. Large security systems are needed to secure information and financial transactions on the Internet, protect personal data, and protect against cyberattacks and hacking.

Legal regulations and laws: In order to ensure cyber security, it is necessary to create laws and regulations covering all digital systems, as well as strengthen international cooperation.

Green economy and digital sustainability

The digital economy should not only be based on technologies, but also ensure sustainable development:

Development of green technologies: Digital economy is also related to energy efficiency, environmental safety, development and use of energy-saving

technologies. Through these, digital technologies play an important role in creating a stable economy.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, we can say that this means ensuring the growth of the economy in a country or region based on digital technologies, the Internet and innovative approaches. For the development of the digital economy, it is necessary to consider several important directions, because this process includes not only technological innovations, but also the social, economic and political environment.

References:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining qarori, 15.06.2021 yildagi 373-son <https://lex.uz/docs/-5458249f>
2. Xudarganov, T., & Allayarov, D. (2024). Iqtisodiyot tarmoqlari sohasida islohatlar va uning nazariy tahlili. *Молодые ученые*, 2(29), 43–46. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/yo/article/view/38545>
3. Allayarov, D. (2024). Sportchilarning sport musobaqlarida ishtirok etishning psixologik xususiyatlari. *UzMU xabarlar*, 1(1.3. 1), 68-71.
4. Allayarov, D. (2024). Talabalar sport faoliyatining psixologik jihatlar va rollari. *Tamaddun nuri jurnali*, 6(57), 277-280.
5. Dilmuradovna, R. Z. (2024). The role of psychology in teaching foreign languages. *Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 28, 11-12.
6. Ruzmetova, Z. (2024). Talabalarda chet tillarni o'rganish jarayonida iroda kuchining namoyon bo'lishi va psixologik xususiyatlari. *tamaddun nuri jurnali*, 6(57), 273-276.
7. Javlonbek Abdullayev. Chop etilgan yili) 2020. Raqamli iqtisodiyotning rivojlanish tendensiyalari va O'zbekistondagi o'rni
8. Abdug'ani O'rinov. (Chop etilgan yili: 2020) Raqamli texnologiyalar va iqtisodiy o'sish.